

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D3.1 Semantic resources

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List of authors, contributors and reviewers

Name	Role	Organization
Andres Garcia-Silva	Author	ESI
Jose Manuel Gomez-Perez	Author	ESI
Raul Ortega	Author	ESI
Esteban González Guardia	Author	UPM

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
API	Application Programming Interface
BNC	British National Corpus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESI	Expert System Iberia
I4OC	Initiative for Open Citations
INGV	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
ISMAR	Istituto di Scienze Marine
SN SciGraph	Springer Nature Science Graph
NER	Named Entity Recognition
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
ROHub	Research Object Hub
RO	Research Object
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UiO	Universitetet i Oslo

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the extension and customization of the text mining and enrichment services that will be integrated in EOSC during RELIANCE. Currently available through ROHub.org, such services provide a variety of scientific communities with text analytics functionalities, contributing to make research data, materials, and results machine-readable and easier to discover by scientists and machines alike¹. Despite being already in operation, these text mining and enrichment services need to be tailored to the specific vocabulary used by the RELIANCE research communities and therefore extended and customized to successfully deliver domain-specific information to such communities.

We start by carrying out a survey where we elicit from the communities the specific fields of research that are relevant for their work, as well as the key journals and venues where they usually communicate their results. Then, we harvest from SciGraph, a knowledge graph of scientific publications released by Springer Nature, a corpus of scientific papers with publications from the last 5 years that belong to such fields of research. The resulting corpus is important for different reasons. First, to enhance the coverage of the scientific terminology supported by the RELIANCE text mining services. Second, to train new language models, either from scratch or by fine-tuning existing pre-trained models, which enable the development of further experimental text mining services based on natural language understanding and machine reading comprehension of scientific documents. Herein, we mainly focus on the former, while the latter will be addressed in forthcoming deliverables.

We run a text mining analysis of our corpus with special attention to the entities, phrases, and concepts, as well as the relationships between them, that were not previously covered by our text mining and enrichment services. Such linguistic artifacts, which represent the missing pieces of information necessary to successfully analyze documents of interest for the RELIANCE communities, are integrated by knowledge engineers and linguists in a knowledge graph. This knowledge graph is called Sensigrafo, a lexico-semantic knowledge graph at the core of the RELIANCE text mining services. As a result of this process, the text mining and enrichment services are enabled to understand the domain terminology used by the target scientific communities in RELIANCE. The resulting text corpus and domain-specific terminology have been released and are publicly available through Zenodo².

In this deliverable, we also introduce pre-trained language models and their application in the context of the RELIANCE text mining and enrichment services. Pre-trained language models like BERT were trained on large general-purpose corpora and have proven to be very useful to tackle different natural language understanding challenges by fine-tuning for specific tasks on domain-specific data. Currently, language models represent the state of the art in many tasks in natural language understanding. In RELIANCE, we plan to use them as a complementary resource to further improve performance in text mining tasks like text classification. In addition, we will explore the application of language models to everyday tasks in a researcher's life that can benefit from machine understanding of natural language, like the comprehension of scientific documents or the analysis of scientific claims.

Finally, this deliverable analyzes other resources that we are planning to leverage in RELIANCE, like the OpenAIRE knowledge graph, which interlinks scientific results, including papers, data, and software, across different repositories. The enrichment of such resources through the RELIANCE text mining and enrichment services will increase their findability by the EOSC communities and support the scalable creation of research objects. We also review the ongoing OpenAIRE open citation initiative, which aims at providing a citation-based graph of research work through OpenAIRE with the potential to become a valuable resource for RELIANCE as well.

¹ J. M. Gomez-Perez, R. Palma and A. Garcia-Silva, "Towards a Human-Machine Scientific Partnership Based on Semantically Rich Research Objects," 2017 IEEE 13th International Conference on e-Science (e-Science), 2017, pp. 266-275, doi: 10.1109/eScience.2017.40.

² https://zenodo.org/record/4721343/files/scigraph_corpus_zenodo.json

2 Introduction

This deliverable reports the resources that are generated to address the text mining and enrichment needs of the RELIANCE research communities. The RELIANCE text mining and enrichment services will be based on the extension and customization of the services deployed in ROHub.org during the EVER-EST project³. Such services are based on expert.ai technology⁴ for natural language processing and understanding, which rely on Sensigrafo⁵, a lexico-semantic knowledge graph that contains approximately 400K lemmas, 300K concepts, and 80 different types of relations, rendering 3 million links between concepts. So far, such services have been successfully applied on scientific domains like Earth Observation and Life Sciences and are currently deployed in the European Space Agency. However, to successfully address the needs of the RELIANCE research communities, further customization needs to be carried out in order to extend and adapt Sensigrafo with the required additional terminology and domain-specific concepts.

As part of the Sensigrafo customization process, first we generate a text corpus of scientific publications driven by relevant research fields for the RELIANCE user communities as a focus group within EOOSC. As source of scientific publications, we use the Springer Nature SciGraph knowledge graph [1], which provides structured metadata, titles and abstracts⁶. Then, we process the resulting corpus to carry out a gap analysis between the vocabulary managed by Sensigrafo and the vocabulary in the corpus. The results of the gap analysis are the input for the Sensigrafo customization. While the primary use of the text corpus is the customization of Sensigrafo, we also plan to use this corpus to learn NLP models from scratch or fine-tune pretrained language models such as BERT⁷ to tackle more experimental text mining services such as the ones to be developed in Task 3.4 - Extended Analytics services in support of the scientific enterprise.

In addition, we analyze OpenAIRE as another important resource for the text mining services. OpenAIRE is a repository of research outputs such as scientific papers, datasets and software, which are distributed among different platforms like arXiv, Zenodo, GitHub, Figshare, and PANGAEA to name a few. We plan to use this repository in addition to ROHub as another source of scientific results that can be integrated in the search and recommendation engine developed as part of the text mining services. For example, the recommendation service retrieves research objects, publications and dataset that are related to the recommendation context defined by the user.

2.1 Scope

This deliverable focuses on the description of the RELIANCE text corpus including its source, the generation process, and the gap analysis between the vocabulary currently managed by the text mining services and the vocabulary in the corpus. It also covers OpenAIRE, its text mining services, and a short introduction to pre-trained language models.

2.2 Audience

While this document is mainly intended for internal use by the RELIANCE consortium, we hope it can also be of interest for OpenAIRE researchers and related initiatives, including the sister projects of RELIANCE. More specifically, the text corpus and the extracted terminology can be relevant for researchers and practitioners with interest in providing additional text mining tools and services for the scientific domains covered in RELIANCE.

³ <https://ever-est.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.expert.ai/products/technology/>

⁵ Sensigrafo is described in section 4.1 of this deliverable.

⁶ SN SciGraph is described in section 3.1 of this deliverable.

⁷ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>

2.3 Structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 3 describes the text corpus that we extract from relevant sources and use to extend and customize the underlying text mining services. We describe SN SciGraph, which is the main source of publications used to build such corpus, the process that we follow to focus on relevant publications for the RELIANCE communities, and the text corpus generation process.
- Section 4 focuses on the terminology analysis of the text corpus. We show different views of the vocabulary extracted from the corpus and identify terms that are candidate to be integrated in Sensigrafo. In addition, we compare the RELIANCE corpus with the BNC general corpus and compute the weirdness index that is used as a hint to identify concepts particularly relevant for the RELIANCE research communities.
- Section 5 provides an overview of the OpenAIRE resources that we plan to leverage in RELIANCE. We focus on the platform, the knowledge graph of scientific outputs, the API, and the initiative for Open Citations I4OC.
- Section 6 ends the document and provides conclusions.

3 Text resources for terminology analysis and learning models

A text corpus covering the scientific domain is necessary to tailor existing text mining tools to the vocabulary used by the target research communities, learn new text mining models from scratch using machine learning techniques, or fine-tune pre-trained models on a particular text mining task. This section is dedicated to the generation of such corpus. First, we describe SN SciGraph, which is the main source of scientific text for our corpus. Then, we present the survey that we conducted with the RELIANCE research communities to identify and select the most relevant fields of research for such communities. Finally, we describe the process we follow to generate the text corpus using a subset of relevant publications from such fields of research.

3.1 Knowledge graph of scientific publications: SN SciGraph

Springer Nature SciGraph⁸ is a knowledge graph of scholarly communications covering funding agencies, research projects, conferences, affiliations, and publications. The main source of information for SciGraph is the Springer Nature editorial group. Thus, SciGraph contains high quality data from trusted and reliable sources. Publications include journals, articles, books, and book chapters from almost two hundred years.

SciGraph is deployed as a linked open data platform that can be browsed interactively using the explorer⁹. The explorer offers a search engine to retrieve any data from the graph and allows to traverse the links connecting this data. In addition, it provides developers with a REST API¹⁰ to access the data, and the datasets are available for download. The data model is encoded using the Resource Description Framework language (RDF) which supports multiple data serializations: JSON-LD, N-Triples, Turtle, or RDF/XML. Most of the data is available with different Creative Commons licenses.

3.1.1 Ontology

SciGraph follows the schema.org specifications. It contains 8 main classes, seven of which are taken from schema.org while the remaining one (Patent) is an ad-hoc entity type.

- schema:ScholarlyArticle describes journal articles;
- schema:Chapter describes book chapters;

⁸ <https://www.springernature.com/gp/researchers/scigraph>

⁹ <https://scigraph.springernature.com/explorer>

¹⁰ <https://dev.springernature.com/>

- schema:Book describes books;
- schema:Periodical describes journals;
- schema:Person describes researchers (e.g., authors, editors, grant recipients)
- schema:MonetaryGrant describes awarded research grants;
- schema:MedicalStudy describes clinical trials;
- sgo:Patent describes patents.

3.1.2 *Field of research classification*

SciGraph uses the schema:about¹¹ property to relate publication to the Fields of Research classification¹² (FOR). FOR includes major fields and related sub-fields of research and emerging areas of study investigated by businesses, universities, national research institutions and other organizations. FOR is a taxonomy with three levels: Divisions (2 digits), Groups (4 digits) and Fields (6 digits). Each Division is based on a broad discipline. Groups within each Division are those which share the same broad methodology, techniques and/or perspective as others in the Division. Each Group is a collection of related Fields of research. Groups and Fields of research are categorized to the Divisions sharing the same methodology rather than the Division they support. An example of Division, Group and Field of research hierarchy is: 09 Engineering (Division), 0901 Aerospace Engineering (Group), 090101 Aerodynamics (Field). The FOR taxonomy has the following 22 divisions:

- 01 Mathematical Sciences
- 02 Physical Sciences
- 03 Chemical Sciences
- 04 Earth Sciences
- 05 Environmental Sciences
- 06 Biological Sciences
- 07 Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences
- 08 Information and Computing Sciences
- 09 Engineering
- 10 Technology
- 11 Medical and Health Sciences
- 12 Built Environment and Design
- 13 Education
- 14 Economics
- 15 Commerce, Management, Tourism and Services
- 16 Studies in Human Society
- 17 Psychology and Cognitive Sciences
- 18 Law and Legal Studies
- 19 Studies in Creative Arts and Writing
- 20 Language, Communication and Culture
- 21 History and Archaeology
- 22 Philosophy and Religious Studies

3.2 *User community survey of relevant fields of research*

Focusing on the domain vocabulary relevant for the research communities in RELIANCE, we conducted a survey around two main topics: i) the relevant fields of research for their work and ii) the journals and venues where the community members publish their contributions. We generated an excel file

¹¹ <http://schema.org/about>

¹² <https://www.arc.gov.au/grants/grant-application/classification-codes-rfcd-seo-and-anzsic-codes>

with the whole FOR taxonomy and asked them to mark the most relevant ones for their work. We provided our researchers with the following guidelines: First, determine the division in which the largest components of your research projects are being performed; then determine the most relevant group within that division; and finally determine the most relevant field within that group. We also advised them to focus on research fields that cover most of the research work (e.g., Volcanology), as opposed to research fields corresponding to specific techniques used in their work (e.g., Analytical Chemistry).

Despite such guidelines, we noticed that researchers also tended to mark as relevant research fields where they do not contribute directly, such as Mathematical Sciences or Computer Science, among others. We understand that, while they certainly use methods and techniques from such fields, their research work is primarily concerned with others like Environmental Sciences or Ecology, where they do contribute. Therefore, after analyzing the survey results and discussing with the user communities about their actual research focus, two main divisions that cover most of their research interest were identified: Earth Sciences and Environmental Sciences. TABLE 1 lists the selected groups and fields of research corresponding to the Earth Sciences and Environmental Sciences divisions.

TABLE 1. Fields of research relevant for the RELIANCE user communities

EARTH SCIENCES	
ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tectonics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atmospheric Aerosols 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Volcanology
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atmospheric Dynamics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geology not elsewhere classified
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atmospheric Radiation 	GEOPHYSICS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate Change Processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical and Electromagnetic Methods in Geophysics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climatology (excl. Climate Change Processes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geodynamics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geophysical Fluid Dynamics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meteorology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geothermics and Radiometrics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tropospheric and Stratospheric Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gravimetrics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atmospheric Sciences not elsewhere classified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Magnetism and Paleomagnetism
GEOCHEMISTRY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seismology and Seismic Exploration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploration Geochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geophysics not elsewhere classified
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inorganic Geochemistry 	OCEANOGRAPHY
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Isotope Geochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biological Oceanography
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic Geochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical Oceanography
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geochemistry not elsewhere classified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical Oceanography
GEOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oceanography not elsewhere classified
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basin Analysis 	PHYSICAL GEOGRAPHY AND ENVIRONMENTAL GEOSCIENCE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extraterrestrial Geology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geomorphology and Regolith and Landscape Evolution
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geochronology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Glaciology
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Igneous and Metamorphic Petrology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydrogeology
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Geoscience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural Hazards
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mineralogy and Crystallography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Palaeoclimatology
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ore Deposit Petrology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quaternary Environments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paleontology (incl. Palynology) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surface Processes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Petroleum and Coal Geology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surfacewater Hydrology
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sedimentology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience not elsewhere classified
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stratigraphy (incl. Biostratigraphy and Sequence Stratigraphy) 	OTHER EARTH SCIENCES

• Structural Geology	• Earth Sciences not elsewhere classified
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	
ECOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS	• Maori Environmental Knowledge
• Ecological Impacts of Climate Change	• Natural Resource Management
• Ecosystem Function	• Pacific Peoples Environmental Knowledge
• Invasive Species Ecology	• Wildlife and Habitat Management
• Landscape Ecology	• Environmental Science and Management not elsewhere classified
• Ecological Applications not elsewhere classified	SOIL SCIENCES
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND MANAGEMENT	• Carbon Sequestration Science
• Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Environmental Knowledge	• Land Capability and Soil Degradation
• Conservation and Biodiversity	• Soil Biology
• Environmental Education and Extension	• Soil Chemistry (excl. Carbon Sequestration Science)
• Environmental Impact Assessment	• Soil Physics
• Environmental Management	• Soil Sciences not elsewhere classified
• Environmental Monitoring	OTHER ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
Environmental Rehabilitation (excl. Bioremediation)	Environmental Sciences not elsewhere classified

3.3 Generation of the RELIANCE text corpus

The RELIANCE text corpus, as we see in Figure 1, is generated applying two filters to the SciGraph Articles Dump: i) Publication Date and ii) Fields of Research. First, we download from SN SciGraph’s site¹³ the articles dump, a compressed file with 10,653 JSON files with the articles along with metadata hosted by its knowledge graph. Once we have the files with all the articles, we select the ones that were published from 2016 to date. Then, we choose the articles that belong to the Earth Sciences or Environmental Sciences fields of research. As a product of this selection process, we obtain a single JSON file, where the text information that forms the RELIANCE corpus is provided by the title and the abstract of those selected articles.

Figure 1. Generation process of the RELIANCE text corpus

¹³ <http://scigraph.downloads.uberresearch.com/archives/current/articles.tar.gz>

Figure 2. Distribution of the RELIANCE corpus among the two main categories: Earth and Environmental Sciences.

The JSON file contains 49.693 articles, with 13M tokens, among which 271k are unique. As shown in Figure 2, the 61% (30.190 articles) of those articles are labeled as Earth Sciences papers, while the rest of them (19.503 articles) belong to the Environmental Sciences field. Moreover, the distributions of the second-level categories are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3. Distribution of the Earth Sciences articles from the RELIANCE corpus among their six subcategories: Geology, Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience, Atmospheric Sciences, Geochemistry, Oceanography and Geophysics.

Figure 4. Distribution of the Environmental Sciences articles from the RELIANCE corpus among their three subcategories: Environmental Science and Management, Soil Sciences and Ecological Applications

4 Terminology analysis

The RELIANCE text corpus allows us to deep dive in the domain vocabulary used by the research communities. The analysis of this corpus is useful to assess and extend terminology coverage in these domains. As a result, the RELIANCE text mining services are now extended with relevant scientific vocabulary. To analyze the text corpus, we use a pre-existing version of the text mining and enrichment services available through ROHub, which is based on expert.ai¹⁴. We leverage its syntactic and semantic capabilities to detect concepts that are not already encoded in the Sensigrafo knowledge graph. Such concepts, along with multiword expression also detected by the software, are used to enrich Sensigrafo. In addition, named entities like people, organization and places are manually inspected to detect errors and improve the accuracy of the NER module. Finally, we carry out a weirdness analysis to detect words that are commonly used in the scientific vocabulary and not so commonly used in the general domain.

4.1 Enriching the text corpus with expert.ai

Expert.ai is a Natural Language Processing and Understanding software that provides a comprehensive set of capabilities, allowing to extract representative metadata from the text. Sensigrafo is a semantic network at its core that represents knowledge as a graph of concepts and relationships between them. The nodes of this knowledge graph are called Syncons, and they are linked to each other through semantic and linguistic relationships in a hierarchical structure. Syncons can contain lemmas, which are words and collocations. The complete meaning of a Syncons comes as a combination of its main elements (grammar type, semantic link, the definition/meaning, the domain, and the frequency relations) and the different kinds of connections (hypernymy, hyponymy) they have with other Syncons. This network results in a greater ability to represent the understanding of a language, which can be adapted to a specific domain, adding new concepts and relations that enrich the metadata extraction and improves text comprehension. In our case, we extend a general-purpose Sensigrafo

¹⁴ <http://expert.ai>

with new terms from the RELIANCE corpus, selecting those that are more representative of the vocabulary used by the communities.

One of the advantages of this approach is that the knowledge graph can be used to **disambiguate** the meaning of a word by recognizing its context. This disambiguation process consists of consecutive phases of analysis including a lexico-grammatical analysis, which identifies, e.g., nouns, proper nouns, and verbs, a syntactical analysis that identifies word groups at different levels, e.g., noun phrases and verb phrases, and a semantic analysis, which finally determines the meaning of each document token according to the knowledge graph. Additionally, the software offers **Named Entity Recognition** capabilities to spot names referenced within the text, such as proper nouns, organizations, and locations.

We process the RELIANCE corpus and extract linguistic metadata from the documents. To this purpose, we feed the text mining services with a piece of text formed by joining the title and the abstract of a paper, generating the following metadata:

- **Domain:** Field or fields of knowledge of the article, based on its main concepts.
- **Organizations:** Organization names or aliases found within the article.
- **People:** People names or aliases found within the article.
- **Places:** Places names or aliases found within the article.
- **Known Concepts:** Proper nouns found in the document and present within the Sensigrafo.
- **Concepts:** Proper nouns found in the document and not present within the Sensigrafo.
- **Main Syncons:** Most frequent concepts from the Sensigrafo mentioned in the text.
- **Main Groups:** Most relevant phrases including multiword expressions found in the text.
- **Main Lemmas:** Most frequent lemmas found in the text.
- **Main Sentences:** Most relevant sentences found in the text.

In addition to this semantic metadata, we include the FOR label of each document to generate a new and enriched JSON file. Then, we index this enriched JSON file with ElasticSearch¹⁵, an open-source search engine based on Lucene. This index allows us to access more easily to the data and display relevant elements in a dashboard, using Kibana¹⁶. This corpus, along with the enriched metadata, can be found in a Zenodo repository¹⁷.

Figure 5. Process to visualize linguistics from the RELIANCE corpus.

4.2 Semantic analysis of the RELIANCE corpus based on Sensigrafo

In Figure 6 we present a tag cloud of the main concepts mentioned in the RELIANCE corpus that are also encoded in Sensigrafo. The tag cloud provides a concise way to see the most frequent and important concepts in our corpus. Note that, while most of the concepts are single words, there are also multiword expressions such as “climate change”, “chemical element”, and “drainage basin”.

¹⁵ <https://www.elastic.co/>

¹⁶ <https://www.elastic.co/es/kibana>

¹⁷ https://zenodo.org/record/4721343/files/scigrafo_corpus_zenodo.json

In TABLE 3 we present the top 15 lemmas present in the corpus which were not encoded in Sensigrafo. To detect these lemmas, we use syntactic analysis and focus mainly on noun phrases. This list of lemmas shows a very different picture of the domain vocabulary. Most of the terms are chemical compounds and measures, and only one multiword expression (sea surface temperature) is in the list. It is not surprising that chemical compounds were not in Sensigrafo since it was not originally conceived to cover Chemistry. Nevertheless, other words in the overall lists of concepts can be integrated in Sensigrafo.

TABLE 3. Top 15 concepts found in the text and not present in Sensigrafo

Lemmas	Count
ha-1	543
kg-1	444
R2	426
NO3	414
18O	387
sea surface temperature	373
Mw	343
SiO2	318
CMIP5	305
m-2	263
year-1	258
U-Pb	254
HCO3	249
SO42	247
GPa	236

Another source of potential concepts to integrate in Sensigrafo are the Main Groups or Multiword expressions detected by the software. Main groups, listed in TABLE 4, are phrases of nouns, verbs and prepositions. Note that a knowledge engineer is needed to determine whether a phrase can be represented as a concept in the knowledge graph and the exact location and form in which such representation needs to be done. This will depend on different factors, such as the possibility of establishing relations with existing concepts or the existence of previous related concepts in the hierarchy.

TABLE 4. Top 10 multiword expressions occurring in the RELIANCE text corpus

Main Groups	Count
soil sample	641
species richness	316
soil moisture	296
climate model	272
groundwater sample	266
soil property	264
land use	263
ecosystem service	233
climate variability	214
soil fertility	200
sediment sample	187

metal concentration	182
groundwater quality	176
soil pH	168
plant species	162

On the other hand, named entities in the corpus can be inspected to detect and fix recognition errors. In TABLE 5 we show the top 15 most frequent named entities found in the corpus. Since these are the most frequent entities there is little chance of error in the detection of entities. However, proper nouns like “Forest” could be further investigated to see if it actually refers to a person or not. In the list of organizations, “sea surface temperature” is clearly a mistake that needs to be addressed in the text mining and enrichment services. The reason for this mistake is that “sea surface temperature” is not encoded in Sensigrafo and therefore the system lacks linguistic information to make the appropriate prediction.

TABLE 5. Top 15 Named entities found in the corpus

People	Count	Places	Count	Organizations	Count
Salvatore Pinto	315	China	4,292	European Community	280
Shannon	135	India	2,074	European Union	247
Ma	53	United States of America	1,366	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change	152
Biochar	50	Iran	972	Cd	144
Linnaeus	50	Europe	838	International Union for Conservation of Nature	136
Anne	48	Japan	757	soil organic carbon	129
April	46	Brazil	710	ECMWF	115
Pb	38	Atlantic Ocean	687	World Health Organization	106
Forest	35	Mediterranean Sea	624	O2 plc	98
Rosby	30	Italy	614	Food and Agriculture Organization	89
Gibbs	29	Russia	601	Environmental Protection Agency	88
Taylor	28	Australia	599	CMIP5	82
Kelly	26	North America	584	sea surface temperature	82
Noah	26	Indian Ocean	562	Amazon	78
Rayleigh	26	Pacific Ocean	491	Fe	77

Finally, in TABLE 6 we present the number of words per metadata type (lemmas, Groups, People, Places, and Organizations) that are included (known) and not included (not known) in Sensigrafo. Note that not all terms need to be included in Sensigrafo. For example, only named entities classified under the wrong entity type need to be integrated in Sensigrafo so that the disambiguation process has more information about them when assigning the correct entity type. The rest of unknown entities correctly classified does not need to be included in Sensigrafo. Similarly, only unknown lemmas and groups that are ambiguous need to be integrated in Sensigrafo so that they can be disambiguated properly. Since there is a considerable number of unknown lemmas, groups and entities, we apply the Pareto principle¹⁸ to focus on the 20% most frequent words for each metadata type. This subset of words is handed to a team of knowledge engineers and linguists in expert.ai that oversee their integration in Sensigrafo. In total, the knowledge engineers need to analyze and process 5070 words. In average

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pareto_principle

they spend 5 minutes per word. So, to process the whole list of words we estimate approximately 2.5 person months. A team of two knowledge engineers can deal with the integration of words in 5 weeks. They have already started, and we expect to finish the process in M5.

TABLE 6. Number of terms described and not described in Sensigrafo.

	Known	Unknown	20% Unknown	Total
Lemmas	2,2978	26,974	556	49,952
Groups	735	171,047	3,121	17,1782
People	1,463	6,520	341	7,983
Places	6,371	20,853	542	27,224
Organizations	1,730	21,755	510	23,485

4.3 Weirdness Index analysis

This index allows comparing the use of a word, based on its frequency, between a domain-specific corpus and a large corpus representing the general language. In this case, we use the British National Corpus (BNC)¹⁹ as the general-purpose corpus. The index, W , is calculated as follow:

$$W = \frac{N_G f_S}{(1 + f_G) N_S}$$

where f_S is the frequency of the word in the specialized corpus, f_G its frequency in the general corpus, the BNC, and N_S , N_G are respectively the number of tokens in the specialized and general corpus. Calculating this index [2] for every token of the RELIANCE corpus, allow us to distinguish the domain-specific terms of the collection. These tokens, sorted by this index, can be found in the Zenodo²⁰ repository of the corpus. In addition, if we filter those concepts, selecting only the ones that are not present in Sensigrafo, we can obtain domain-specific terms that can be potentially used to extend and enrich the knowledge graph, such as the terms in Table 7. Furthermore, the terms with a low weirdness index will represent general concepts, which may appear in broader-domain texts and are therefore not interesting for the purpose of generating a domain-specific terminology.

Table 7. Top 10 terms with the highest and lowest weirdness index occurring in the RELIANCE text corpus

Lemmas with highest WI	Weirdness index	Lemmas with lowest WI	Weirdness index
ENSO	17,250.2	Win	0.0043
N2O	9,480.3	Money	0.0042
CMIP5	7,443.28	Studio	0.0039
Modelling	5,665.83	Pupil	0.0039
WRF	4,847.59	Terry	0.0037
NDVI	4,598.33	Worry	0.0033
Downscaling	4,280.32	Sat	0.0032
GCMs	4,237.34	Hat	0.0031
LULC	4,048.25	Employee	0.003
RCP8.5	3,850.57	Mood	0.0028
GHG	3,850.57	Speech	0.0024
Cd	3,695.24	Teacher	0.0022
137Cs	3,489.58	Mr.	0.0019

¹⁹ <https://www.english-corpora.org/bnc/>

²⁰ https://zenodo.org/record/4721343/files/reliance_weirdness_filtered.json

Rhizosphere	3,386.44	Mrs.	0.0009
WNP	3,240.32	Me	0.0003

To extend Sensigrafo with specific terms, we analyze the distribution of the weirdness index over the whole set of terms from the RELIANCE corpus and search for a threshold to narrow the selection. In Figure 7, we can see how most of the terms have a weirdness index lower than one, and how the distribution follows a long tail from that point on. The term selection is made by using the accumulated weirdness index of the whole collection. Again, we apply Pareto to select the terms that accumulate 80% of the total accumulated weirdness index. This results in 5,219 concepts that are representative of this specific domain and can therefore be used to enrich and improve comprehension of the documents in the RELIANCE corpus.

Figure 7. Histogram of the Weirdness Index of terms within the RELIANCE corpus. X-axis represents the weirdness index and the Y-axis the number of appearances.

5 Metadata repositories to exploit in the text mining services

We plan to extend the RELIANCE text mining and enrichment services by exploiting the OpenAIRE Research Graph, which connects papers, software, and data across several repositories. By adding OpenAIRE as another source in addition to ROHub, our services, particularly those for search and recommendation, benefit from a wide range of publications, code repositories, and datasets. The goal of OpenAIRE is to bring openness and transparency to the research process, making science useful to different members of the society. We can highlight some of these features:

- **Open science services provision.** All of them are present in the EOSC Marketplace. These services can be used by any kind of user to start working on Open Science. Plus, they are interconnected providing an interoperability framework.
- **Link research.** OpenAIRE links the outcomes of a research (funders, data, and software) enabling discoverability and reproducibility in the knowledge generated. *These links* can be traceable using the OpenAIRE Research Graph that can be described more in detail in the next sections.
- **Monitor Open Science.** OpenAIRE has developed a set of services used to exploit the data indexed in their platform. These services can be used: i) to monitor the research done by you or your community or ii) to monitor the research funded by your institution. These services

exploit the OpenAIRE Research Graph. In the case of RELIANCE, we are interested in exploiting the OpenAIRE Research Graph model to identify linked resources to offer text mining services. The OpenAIRE project finished last year. Nevertheless, the initiative continues in the form of the OpenAIRE Nexus project. We will monitor the services as they are updated and created by this new project to analyze the impact of these new developments in RELIANCE.

5.1 OpenAIRE: software, data, papers

OpenAIRE has developed and deployed a repository, Zenodo, where every researcher can deposit any outcome of their research. It includes data, software, papers, video, audio, etc. All these outcomes are indexed in the OpenAIRE Research Graph that can be queried using the API or an SPARQL endpoint. These features turn this platform into an interesting entry point to discover new knowledge. OpenAIRE integrates Zenodo with GitHub, a platform used to share and to control the different versions of the software generated in a project. A Zenodo account can be linked with a GitHub account in such a way that when a user releases a version of the software, this is automatically published in the corresponding Zenodo account as a .zip file. Like ROHub, Zenodo also generates DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) and supports the FAIR principles. In the next table, we show the metadata used in Zenodo:

TABLE 8. List of metadata in Zenodo

Name	Description
Filename	The filenames uploaded in a record. ZIP files can be included, and its content will be visible in the preview component
Communities	The communities where the record will be indexed. In Zenodo, a record can belong to different communities, which means that will be visible inside this community, if the curator accepts it.
Upload Type	The type of the resource deposited. It can be Publication, Poster, Presentation, Dataset, Image, Video/Audio, Software, Lesson, Physical Object or Other.
Publication Type	It has multiple options such as book, Data Management Plan, Project Deliverable, and Patent.
Digital Object Identifier	This is a persistent identifier generated automatically by Zenodo to identify the resources deposited.
Publication date	The date of the publication
Title	The title of the resource
Authors	The list of authors of the resource. Optionally, the ORCID can be included.
Description	A description of the resource
Version	Version of the resource
Language	Language of the resource
Keywords	Keyword to describe your resource. It is a free text; no vocabulary is needed.
Additional notes	This metadata is used in case you want to include additional information
Access right	An owner can establish different rights to access to the resource: i) Open Access (public), ii) Embargoed Access (it is private until an specific date), iii) Restricted Access (a user needs to ask for permission to the owner) and iv) Closed Access (private)
License	The user can choose the license of its resource
Grants	The user can add the different funders of the project.
Related identifiers	Related resources can be added to it. A relation can be included such as: i) cites this upload, ii) is previous version of this upload, iii) is part of this upload, iv)

	documents this upload or v) compiled/created this upload. The type of the related resource can be added too.
Contributors	A list of users that have been contributed to the resource.
References	A list of references can be added to the resource as metadata
Subjects	Subjects can be added using a controlling vocabulary with this field.

Zenodo has an API to interact with the platform. However, the API is only focused on methods to deposit resources. To access the resources, the OAI-PMH protocol must be used. OAI-PMH is focused on the transmission of metadata, allowing data harvesting from the repository. The entire repository or a specific community can be harvested depending on the requirements defined. All the metadata is licensed under Creative Commons Zero. The Zenodo API has a rate limit that restrict the usage to avoid overloading the system. The different formats of the metadata are:

- `oai_datacite`: This format is composed by: i) the resources described following the last Datacite OAI schema and ii) other elements describing the version of the metadata.
- `datacite`: The original DataCite schema. It is not compatible with OAI-PMH version 2
- `oai_datacite3`: Version 3.0 of the Data OAI schema.
- `datacite3`: Version 3.0 of the DataCite schema
- `oai_dc`: In this case, the Dublin Core schema is used.
- `marc21`: export format primarily supported for legacy reasons.

While Zenodo offers endpoints to access the data and metadata, we plan to use OpenAIRE API which give us access to Zenodo and the rest of integrated sources.

5.2 OpenAIRE API

According to the OpenAIRE team: “The OpenAIRE Research Graph is an open resource that aggregates a collection of research data properties (metadata, links) available within the OpenAIRE Open Science infrastructure for funders, organizations, researchers, research communities and publishers to interlink information by using a semantic graph database approach.”

Figure 8 depicts the different components of this graph. The graph links projects, organizations and authors with different resources (publications, datasets, software, and other research products). Funders can be identified indirectly through projects. As it has been mentioned previously, Zenodo is one of the contributors but institutional repositories can be registered in the system for harvesting their metadata. This graph can be re-used or even downloaded freely because it is licensed with CC-BY. One interesting service they provide for our project is the processing of full texts to infer new links and enrich the graph. There are two ways to query this graph: the REST API and the SPARQL endpoint. In this section, we focus on the API and the SPARQL end point is described in the next section. The OpenAIRE HTTP API allows developers to access metadata records of the OpenAIRE Research Graph. This API is designed only for discoverability and exploration purposes. It means that the whole information space cannot be downloaded using the API. In addition, the number of results returned on a request is limited to 10,000 requests.

Figure 8. OpenAIRE Research Graph components

A complete list of the requests and parameters can be found in the OpenAIRE HTTP API webpage. The API gives supports the following entities:

- Publications
- Research data
- Software
- Other Research Products
- Projects

Each entity has a specific endpoint. The schema of the point is the following: <http://api.OpenAIRE.eu/search/<entity>>. These requests have a common set of parameters. For our purpose, we highlight the following parameters in TABLE 9.

TABLE 9. List of common parameters

PARAMETER	OPTION	DESCRIPTION
page	integer	Page number
size	integer	Results per page used in conjunction with the page parameter to paginate results
format	json xml csv tsv	Format of the response.
sortBy	sortBy=field,[ascending descending]	Sorting of the results.
keywords	white-space separated list of keywords	List of keywords

The text mining services will exploit the Publication entity, which comprises papers, software and data. Next table resumes the main parameters that will be used to this purpose:

TABLE 10. Publication entity parameters in OpenAIRE API

PARAMETER	OPTION	DESCRIPTION
sortBy	sortBy=field, [ascending descending]	The sorting order of the specific field
doi	List of DOIs separated by comma	Gets the publications with these DOIs
OpenAIREPublicationID	List of OpenAIRE identifiers separated by comma	Gets the publications with the OpenAIRE identifiers
fromDateAccepted	Format: YYYY-MM-DD	Gets the publications with a date greater or equal than the given date
toDateAccepted	Format: YYYY-MM-DD	Gets the publications with a date less or equal than the given date
title	List of titles separated by white-space	Gets the publications with contains the words given
author	Names or surnames separated by white-space	Gets publications by authors
OpenAIREProviderID	List of identifiers separated by comma	Search for publications by OpenAIRE data provider identifier.
OpenAIREProjectID	List of identifiers separated by comma	Search for publications by OpenAIRE project identifier
projectID	---	The grant identifier of the project
OA	true false	Gets the publications available in OpenAccess or not.
country	2 letter country code	Search for publications associated to the country code.

5.3 OpenAIRE research graph dump

The OpenAIRE research graph is a resource that aggregates a collection of research data properties (metadata, links). The schema of the research graph is described here. In this schema, four entities can be identified: result, organization, data source and project:

Figure 9. OpenAIRE schema

- Result schema describes the elements and properties of the OpenAIRE Result entity. This entity represents digital objects resulting from the scientific process. Different metadata fields such as title, country, publisher, persistent identifier, and citations can be found. Note that some of these metadata has a link with the metadata used by Zenodo (see 5.1).
- The organization schema describes the companies, research centers or institutions involved in the project. This information is collected from CORDIS or from registries of institutions like re3Data. This schema has interesting elements such as legal name, website url, pids, country, etc.

- The data source schema describes the different data sources such as public repositories, dataset archives, CRIS systems, etc. This schema has properties such as official name, website url, contact email, data source type, description, subjects, collected from, etc. The values of a data source type following a specific vocabulary.
- The project schema describes the projects that generate the research resources (result). Funders can be discovered through this entity. This entity has properties such as code (given by funders), title, contact email, website url, start date, end date, etc.

OpenAIRE has developed a specific ontology to allow semantic queries against the OpenAIRE research graph. The entities described are: ResultEntry, Organization, DataSource and Project. These are the same entities described above. This ontology uses terms from other ontologies such as skos, dcterms, foaf, schema, dcite, rdfs, etc. To make queries using this ontology, OpenAIRE has deployed a specific SPARQL endpoint. The availability of this service will depend on the number of clients requesting results. Periodically, every two months the team of OpenAIRE publishes the RDF dump in Zenodo. We consider the option to publish this dump locally to avoid the limitations imposed by the remote SPARQL endpoint.

We used the SPARQL endpoint to retrieve some statistics about the information encoded in the knowledge graph. In TABLE 11 and TABLE 12 we show the number of instances of the main Classes in OpenAIRE ontology and the number of triples that use any of the ad-hoc relations. There are 43.8M of research outcomes in the knowledge graph. Among the ad-hoc relations there are 377M annotations using the subject predicate that indicates the research area of the outcome. We filter the subjects for those relevant for RELIANCE including Environmental Science and Earth Sciences and find that there are 616.092 research outcomes in these categories (see TABLE 13). In TABLE 14 we can see that most research results in OpenAIRE are publications, and datasets and software are just a small fraction of these outcomes.

TABLE 11. Classes in OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph

Classes	Instances
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	43,862,943
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ProjectEntity	2,722,935
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/DatasourceEntity	24,870
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/OrganizationEntity	23,438

TABLE 12. Object properties in OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph.

Object Properties (relations)	Triples
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/outcome	2,469,655
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/similarity	20,94,992
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/publicationDataset	219,459
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/relationship	6,441,243
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/affiliation	40,882,502
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/supplement	201,629
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/citation	13,096
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/subject	377,103,230
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/review	1,476

TABLE 13. Result Entities with subjects relevant for RELIANCE

Subjects (Research fields)	Instances
"Environmental science"	522,607
"Earth and Planetary Sciences (miscellaneous)"	52,141
"Environmental Science (miscellaneous)"	16,513
"Environmental Sciences not elsewhere classified"	13,093
"Earth science"	11,735

TABLE 14. Types available for result entity in OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph.

Result entity	Instances
publication	29,682,187
dataset	1,767,269
other	450,424
software	4,064
N/A	12,699,924
Total	44,603,868

5.4 Text Mining in OpenAIRE

Figure 10 shows the general workflow of the information inference framework in OpenAIRE [3]. Some of the high-level nodes in the workflow are text mining tasks such as document content analysis, document classification, document clustering and document similarity. The goal of document content analysis is to obtain bibliography metadata (cited by), funding metadata (funded by), and reference metadata linking papers and datasets. Document classification is used to label documents, for example with categories in the arXiv taxonomy based on the document content and metadata. Document clustering aims at grouping similar documents based on their content and metadata. Finally, document similarity is used to avoid integrating duplicated documents in the knowledge graph.

Figure 10. Information Inference Framework in OpenAIREplus. Figure taken from [3]

Since the authors mention neither the techniques that were used to develop each of such text mining tasks nor to what extent they have implemented and integrated these services in OpenAIRE, we query the knowledge graph using the Sparql endpoint for relationships between the different research

results. In TABLE 15 we show for each research result type (publication, dataset, and software) the main object properties. The `publicationDataset` object property relates publications and datasets, and datasets to publications. In total, there are more than 130K of such relations. Nevertheless, manually inspecting some examples we realize that some datasets related to publications in the knowledge graph were not actually datasets but publications. The `similarity` object property is widely populated for the three types of research results. However, we cannot find scientific or technical documentation explaining how these relations are identified, and the quality of the annotations is not reported. Thus, the RELIANCE text mining services can be used not only to enrich OpenAIRE research results relevant for our user communities with useful metadata and relations, but also to provide a baseline that allows comparing our annotations with the existing annotations in OpenAIRE.

TABLE 15. Relations per result entity type including the classes used as range.

Object property (relations)	Total # triples	Range (class type of the object property target)	Type of result entity
Publication			
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/affiliation	4,486,878	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/OrganizationEntity	
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/outcome	848,492	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ProjectEntity	
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/publicationDataset	135,198	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/similarity	13,457,891	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset, other, publication, software
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/relationship	823	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset, other, publication
Dataset			
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/subject	111	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#inverseFunctionalProperty	
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/supplement	3,487	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/publicationDataset	139,885	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	other, publication
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/citation	802	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/outcome	47,561	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ProjectEntity	
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/similarity	5,296,531	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset, other, publication, software
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/review	9	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/relationship	195,024	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset, other, publication
Software			
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/outcome	513	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ProjectEntity	
http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/similarity	9,875	http://lod.openaire.eu/vocab/ResultEntity	dataset, other, publication, software

5.5 OpenAIRE open citations

In addition to the papers, software, and data we are interested in the OpenAIRE citation graph. Currently OpenAIRE is actively involved in the Open Citations initiative, which is an independent infrastructure organization for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open bibliographic and citation data by the use of Semantic Web (Linked Data) technologies. The data model defines different entities (see the full ontology in Figure 9):

- Published bibliographic resources. It describes bibliographic resources.
- Possible resource embodiments. It defines the digital format.
- Bibliographic references. It describes the references used to cite.
- Responsible agents. People or organizations involved in the bibliographic resource (author, publisher, etc.).
- Roles.
- Citations. It links two bibliographic resources.
- Identifiers. It defines external identifiers such as ORCID, DOI, etc.

Figure 11. Open Citations Ontology

The work of OpenAIRE in the Open Citations initiative is ongoing. So, RELIANCE will need to keep track of their progress. When the OpenAIRE citation data is available we can use it in the text mining service to measure the research influence in both ways: who and what influences my research and who and what is influenced by my research.

6 Pre-trained language models

In RELIANCE we plan to use state of the art neural language models to further develop text mining and enrichment capabilities involving machine understanding of scientific documents. Before introducing language models, we start this section describing how text needs to be represented to be processed by neural networks and in general any machine learning approach. To inject text in machine learning including neural networks it needs to be converted in a numerical representation. There are different numerical representations for text like the bag of words model using vector representations. Nevertheless, in this representations word order is not important and the number of dimensions in is the number of words in the vocabulary. Since this number is always large, it was difficult for neural networks particularly to fit these representations in memory. In addition, the main drawback of the bag or word models is that it fails to capture the meaning of words. It only provides representation based on the frequency of words at the document or collection level.

Distributed word representations, on the other hand, are based on the distributional hypothesis where words that co-occur in similar context are considered to have similar (or related) meaning. Word embedding algorithms yield dense vectors so that words with similar distributional context appear in the same region in the embedding space. word embeddings, have been used with great success in NLP tasks such as part-of-speech tagging, chunking, named entity recognition, semantic role labeling and synonym detection. Nevertheless, early word embeddings algorithms like Word2Vec [4] and GloVe [5] generate static word embeddings that fail to capture the meaning of ambiguous words when they are used in different context. This means that a word embedding is always the same regardless of the sentence where the word appears, e.g., “Paris” would have the same embedding either as a city or as a celebrity.

To generate contextual word embeddings, language models like ELMo [6] and BERT [7], were proposed. A neural language model [8] is a model that is trained to predict the next word in a sequence given some previous words. These language models are learnt from high-quality and large text corpus like Wikipedia, and BookCorpus. Fine-tuning pre-trained language models by transferring internal representations to a task-specific shallow feed forward networks have advanced the state of the art in many NLP tasks.

6.1 BERT

BERT [7] (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) is a neural model based on Transformers [9], that uses a multi-head attention mechanism that can be trained to learn relations between words (or word pieces). In contrast to previous models, BERT does not read the text sequentially (left-to-right or right-to-left) but the whole sequence at once. This feature allows the model to learn the context of each token of the sequence. BERT takes pieces of text as input, that are embedded into vectors and processed in the neural network. During the training, the model assigns and refines contextual representations for each token, using the attention heads.

Figure 12. Overall pre-training and fine-tuning procedures for BERT (took from the paper BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding).

The potential of BERT lies in its training as a Language Model. After feeding BERT with a huge quantity of unlabeled pieces of text where some words are masked, the model can learn high-level representations of tokens, based on their context. As a result, the pretrained BERT model can be used in several downstream tasks as Question Answering or Text Classification, as shown in Figure 12. The latter can be easily modeled, using the contextual representation of each token of the sequence generated by BERT, then putting it together as one vector, and using this joint embedding to classify the text following a specific taxonomy with a dense neuronal layer.

6.2 RoBERTa

We can use also other similar models as RoBERTa [10] (Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach), an optimized model based on transformers that came out from a replication study of BERT pretraining. RoBERTa improves the training procedure, removing the Next Sentence Prediction task from BERT’s pretraining and changing the masked tokens in each epoch. Furthermore, RoBERTa increases the size of the corpus used to pretrain the language model from 16 GB (Books Corpus and English Wikipedia) to 160 GB (CommonCrawl News Dataset, Web Text Corpus and Stories from Common Crawl). As a result, RoBERTa outperforms BERT on GLUE benchmarking tasks.

6.3 Language models in RELIANCE text mining services

We foresee different applications of pre-trained language models in the RELIANCE text mining and enrichment services, ranging from the classification of research articles into fields of research to other services focused on natural language understanding and machine comprehension of scientific text, like the ones described in Task 3.4 of the RELIANCE Grant Agreement (Extended analytics services). Regarding classification, we plan to use language models as an additional way to train classifiers that are able to predict the fields of research of a scientific document. To this purpose, fine-tuning language models like BERT over a single sequence classification is the usual approach [7]. In terms of understanding and machine comprehension, we plan to explore additional functionalities such as determining the novelty of a particular scientific contribution or idea based on its textual description, analyzing to what extent scientific claims are supported or refuted by the existing state of the art, and supporting the comprehension of scientific literature by the researchers. Calculating a novelty score is based on the notion of document similarity, since similar documents can indicate low novelty. In this respect, language models like BERT and others have been used successfully to compute document similarity. In addition, language models can also be fine-tuned on a classification task to predict whether a scientific claim is supported or not by the existing literature [11]. Finally, pre-trained

language models can help to support reading comprehension, as in [12]. Modeling the text provided by the RELIANCE corpus with a transformer and then training the model to generate questions or hypotheses [13] based on the content of a research paper can assist third-party researchers to find similar articles or distill the main ideas from it.

7 Conclusions

We identify and generate resources to extend and customize the RELIANCE text mining services. The analysis of the vocabulary in the text corpus that we generate by covering the domains of interest of the RELIANCE research communities shows that such vocabulary is different from the vocabulary in a general corpus. We show that while Sensigrafo covers scientific terminology to some extent, such coverage is far from being complete. Therefore, we identify candidate concepts to be integrated in Sensigrafo, including lemmas, entities, and groups of words that are not already covered in our knowledge graph. In addition, we compute the weirdness index to identify frequent words used in the scientific domain that are not used in a general domain. Words with a higher weirdness index are also suggested as candidate concepts to be integrated in the Sensigrafo. We define a plan for the integration of this vocabulary in Sensigrafo, which is carried out by knowledge engineers and linguists. On the other hand, we analyze the OpenAIRE platform as a new data source to be leveraged by the RELIANCE text mining services. With access to OpenAIRE, these services shall increase their coverage of research outputs beyond research objects by adding papers, datasets, and software. In addition, we assess the Open Citations initiative supported by OpenAIRE to have access to the citation graph of the research publications. This citation graph can be used to calculate the research influence of a given paper or author. Nevertheless, the OpenAIRE work in the initiative is just starting and will progress in parallel with the execution of RELIANCE. Therefore, we will keep track of their progress and continuously assess the feasibility of their application in accordance with the expected technology readiness level (TRL).

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